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Статтю присвячено вивченню можливостей та обмежень використання ChatGPT та інших нейромереж, що базуються на технологіях штучного інтелекту, в освітній та дослідницькій діяльності на курсі іноземної мови. В умовах швидкого розвитку ШІ технологій виникає дискусія серед педагогів-практиків і дослідників щодо допустимості та ефективності застосування таких інструментів студентами. У статті виокремлюються ключові аспекти використання ChatGPT на заняттях з іноземної мови, включно з його здатністю генерувати іншомовні тексти на основі запитів, потенціалом в опрацюванні великих масивів даних, формулюванні актуальності дослідження та проведенні оглядів іноземної літератури. При цьому наголошується на необхідності відповідальності за результати «спільної» роботи зі ШІ та дотримання норм авторської етики з огляду на ризики плагіату та недостовірної інформації, яку надає ChatGPT.

Автори розглядають вплив широкого впровадження нейромереж на когнітивні здібності студентів, їхню здатність критично оцінювати дані та проводити повноцінні наукові дослідження. У статті також порушується питання про необхідність розвитку вмінь формулювати точні запити для ШІ іноземною мовою, аналізувати та перевіряти отриману інформацію. ChatGPT може стати корисним інструментом для виконання рутинних завдань, однак залишається важливим зберегти баланс між використанням технологій і традиційними методами наукової роботи, що вимагають глибокого аналізу та критичного мислення. Авторська етика та питання достовірності даних стають центральними аспектами, які необхідно враховувати при інтеграції ChatGPT у дослідницьку діяльність на курсі іноземної мови.

Abstract

The article examines the potential and limitations of using ChatGPT and other AI neural networks in foreign language education and research. Teachers and researchers are debating the acceptability and effectiveness of using AI tools by students due to the rapid development of AI technologies. The article highlights key considerations for effectively incorporating ChatGPT into foreign language instruction. It demonstrates the tool's ability to generate query-based texts in multiple languages, handle large data sets, and assist in research relevance and literature reviews in foreign languages. The importance of maintaining accountability for the outcomes of "collaborative" efforts with AI is underscored, alongside strict adherence to ethical authorship, due to the potential risks of plagiarism and the dissemination of inaccurate information from ChatGPT.

The authors examine how the widespread use of neural networks affects students' cognitive skills, particularly their ability to critically assess data and perform meaningful scientific research. The article also raises the issue of the need to develop the skills to formulate accurate queries for AI in a foreign language, analyze and verify the obtained information. ChatGPT can be a useful tool for routine tasks, but it remains important to maintain a balance between the use of technology and traditional methods of scientific work that require deep analysis and critical thinking. Author ethics and issues of data validity become central aspects to be considered when integrating ChatGPT into research activities in a foreign language course.

Ключові слова: ChatGPT, штучний інтелект, нейромережі, дослідницька робота, авторська етика, плагіат, курс іноземної мови.

Keywords: ChatGPT, artificial intelligence, neural networks, research work, author's ethics, plagiarism, foreign language course.

Problem statement. Modern AI technologies greatly affect education, especially in student and scientist research activities. ChatGPT is a popular chatbot that generates text responses to user questions. Its wide-ranging language and cognitive skills have sparked debate among scientists and educators. Some want to ban these technologies in education, while others support using them carefully in student research projects.

The challenge lies in finding a balance that maximizes the benefits while minimizing potential drawbacks. Educators must promote digital literacy and critical thinking as they explore innovative ways to integrate AI tools. Proponents argue that with proper guidance, AI can enhance critical thinking and facilitate deeper learning. Ultimately, finding a balance between harnessing its benefits and maintaining academic integrity will be essential for the future of education. It is no longer possible to completely ban students from using artificial intelligence technologies. It is now impossible to ban students from using artificial intelligence technologies, such as ChatGPT, in education and research. We believe it's important to discuss ChatGPT's potential, the responsibility for outcomes in its use, the risks of working with neural networks, and how to train students to effectively use ChatGPT for research, term papers, and qualifications. Proponents argue that when used responsibly, AI can enhance learning by providing personalized support and resources. This could lead to a more engaging and effective educational experience, fostering critical thinking and creativity among students.

Literature review. Researchers emphasize different aspects of ChatGPT technology in their definitions according to the field of knowledge they represent. In particular, Hwang G.J., Chang C.Y. define a chatbot as "a technology application model that effectively facilitates interpersonal communication and learning and provides various types of information through interactive and easy-to-use interfaces". Authors: Io H.N., Lee C.B [2] "a dialog agent that has the ability to interact or 'communicate' with a human in natural language".

Analyzing the above definitions allows us to highlight several key aspects relevant to the use of chatbots in learning. A chatbot is a program developed on the basis of artificial intelligence technologies such as natural language and machine learning. The program acts according to the algorithms of human speech behavior pre-installed in it. In today's technology-driven world, there is a plethora of chatbots available that excel in interacting with users of various programs, catering to a wide range of languages. Advanced chatbots are designed to deliver genuine responses, showcasing a deep understanding of language and communication. They use language and speech techniques to engage users in meaningful and personalized conversations. They can use language and speech mechanisms to have conversations with users that are both relevant and feel personalized. Interacting with these chatbots can be very enriching and informative for users from different linguistic backgrounds. Chatbots are able to take on the function of a teacher to provide students and learners with feedback when doing homework or conducting project activities (from answering frequently asked

questions to evaluating the stages of completing assignments or projects). The interaction with a chatbot involves spoken or written communication between the learner and the chatbot.

Thorp H defines ChatGPT as a program that automatically generates text from prompts.

A prompt is a request that guides ChatGPT and other neural networks to create text or images. It is the accuracy of queries that determines the content, volume and meaningful depth of ChatGPT responses and their relevance to the task at hand. In their study, Dis van E.A.M., Bollen J., and Rooij van R. offer an in-depth exploration of the natural functioning of ChatGPT [4]. Scientists claim that ChatGPT is a huge language system based on machine learning, capable of autonomous learning on a large array of data and information and creating complex texts that can be characterized as scientific. Such a definition quite accurately reveals the feature of ChatGPT - its ability to autonomously learn from massive amounts of data, and generate texts by analyzing the learned material. Neural networks and ChatGPT technology are still at the beginning of their journey. They have already shown educators and scientists the ability to write essays, review literature, analyze data, and compose poetry, but not yet the ability to write computer code or perform statistical calculations. Soon, this technology will reach the level of turnkey research writing, peer review, and decision-making for publishing research articles in journals.

The objective of this study is to conduct a review of research on the use of chatbots in general and ChatGPT in particular in research; to identify and discuss key issues related to the effectiveness of using ChatGPT in undergraduate research in a foreign language course.

The statement of the main material. ChatGPT's technology is widely used in foreign language teaching methodology. It creates conditions for genuine foreign language practice for students, which is crucial for learning a language outside its cultural setting.

ChatGPT and other analog programs, which will appear and dynamically develop every year, are first distinguished by their accessibility. Undergraduate and graduate students can use AI-based programs in their research. It is pointless to ban students from using ChatGPT for searching and processing information. Developing skills in neural networks is crucial for novice researchers to maximize their productivity. At the same time, each user should realize the responsibility for compliance with the norms of author's ethics and possible threats related to the authenticity of materials provided by ChatGPT.

Many scholars have argued that ChatGPT is capable of generating significant amounts of text in response to user queries. As numerous examples show ChatGPT can be an aid to the professionally competent user, in general ChatGPT is able to solve some (but by no means all) of the problems in producing research texts. In particular, ChatGPT is able to formulate the relevance of the research, conduct a literature review (from definitions of concepts to the presentation of concepts, models, etc., often following its logic to carry out analytical work, and compile a bibliography. However,

users should keep in mind that the quality of the results depends on how well they phrase their queries, and ChatGPT cannot guarantee the accuracy of the information provided. To ensure meaningful outcomes, researchers must critically evaluate the generated content and supplement it with their expertise and judgement. By combining the capabilities of ChatGPT with rigorous scholarly practices, novice researchers can enhance their writing process while maintaining academic integrity.

Unlike many other dialog programs that do not retain the topic of the discussion in their memory, ChatGPT demonstrates the ability to remember the context and topic of the discussion. The researcher can introduce ChatGPT to the topics for the upcoming conversation with the first message.

The widespread use of ChatGPT in education could harm learners' intellectual and cognitive abilities, as they may become overly dependent on artificial intelligence. They will gradually lose the ability to think critically and analytically about information, including task formulation, material searches, data analysis and classification, summarization, critical thinking, and drawing conclusions.

In addition, the use of ChatGPT in research work will require users to develop new additional skills in formulating specific and precise queries to obtain the information they are looking for. In this regard, it seems important to combine traditional forms and methods of working with scientific information and innovative data processing tools.

Author ethics of writing research texts is one of the important aspects of ChatGPT integration in education and research work. In a number of papers, our foreign colleagues raised issues related to authorship, mass plagiarism and, as a result, banning the use of ChatGPT in educational institutions. The responses to the user's queries clearly originate from ChatGPT. Following this logic, it should be awarded a qualification or degree for a significant amount of work done and authorship of a scientific text. Copying the results of ChatGPT's analytical activities into research papers will always be an act of unauthorized borrowing or plagiarism. Some researchers believe that it is necessary to require authors of research papers to include in the content of manuscripts a description or report of which sections of the research text were written/compiled using ChatGPT [4]. At the present stage, ChatGPT can help the researcher to select material and partially process it. But as technology advances, it will be difficult or impossible to identify the true authorship of the text. In this regard, the issues of authors' compliance with the ethics of scientific writing will be constantly in the focus of attention of the scientific community and the subject of discussion in the academic environment.

At this stage, ChatGPT, like most chatbots, cannot adjust its language to match the user's proficiency level. Experience with chatbots, including ChatGPT, highlights that AI's inability to adapt speech limits its use in education and research. ChatGPT is able to produce largely scientific-like texts, but the level of this "scientific" does not vary. This rigidity can hinder effective communication, especially when addressing diverse

audiences with varying levels of understanding. Consequently, this presents a challenge in creating more inclusive learning environments where users can benefit from tailored interactions [5].

At this current stage of technological development, although neural networks have not reached a level of intellectual capability that can rival that of a trained scientist, the essential role of the educator is to guide the younger generation in understanding the immense potential that artificial intelligence holds in enhancing and facilitating scientific research. This includes teaching students how AI can significantly reduce the time spent on critical tasks such as searching for relevant literature, selecting appropriate citations, and identifying specific scientific components that are necessary for thorough analysis and comparison. By doing so, educators can empower future researchers to harness these tools effectively, ultimately allowing them to focus more on the creative and innovative aspects of scientific inquiry rather than being bogged down by preliminary work. Thus, fostering a deep comprehension of AI's role in research will better prepare students for the evolving landscape of science and technology. However, in-depth analysis, generalization and comparison conclusions, and the generation of new knowledge (for now) remain the privilege of the scientist.

Studying the experience of other scientists in the use of artificial intelligence in research work allows us to conclude that ChatGPT is not able to immediately (on the first request) provide the user with comprehensive information on the topic of the research work. Some users on the Internet note that the volume of the query can reach one and a half pages. The query results obtained can and should raise questions related to the validity and reliability of the data obtained. ChatGPT sometimes misrepresents and incompletely presents scientific information. The use of knowingly false raw data will certainly lead to false results. ChatGPT's resources are limited to the databases to which its developers have defined access [6]. In this regard, in cases where ChatGPT is unable to find and provide certain information, including scientific data, it starts making them up by providing non-existent definitions of concepts, classifications, models or references to literature.

All these issues related to the validity and reliability of information obtained from ChatGPT and neural networks will force every researcher to cross-check it thoroughly. This will prove to be quite time and resource consuming. In this regard, for many researchers, traditional and familiar methods of working with scientific information and writing scientific papers will be more effective than innovative ones. At least at the present stage.

Given the complexities and risks of using ChatGPT in research, it raises an important question about the user's expertise in the relevant professional field. This question raises an important point about whether a person has the skills and knowledge to use advanced AI tools effectively. Therefore, one cannot overlook the implication that a user's competence may heavily influence the quality, reliability, and validity of

the research outcomes when employing ChatGPT. Experience shows that only having professional competence in a given field of communication, it is possible to formulate, reformulate and clarify queries, to assess the importance and significance of the information provided by ChatGPT (definitions or classifications, analytical data), as well as to assess the validity and reliability of the data. It is questionable to recommend ChatGPT to students and novice researchers who may lack the expertise to evaluate the reliability of the information it provides.

Conclusion and further research prospects. ChatGPT can significantly enhance the research efforts of scientists and students. It reduces the time and effort spent on finding and processing literature sources and relevant data. Additionally, it can assist in the compilation of research texts, allowing users to focus on more critical aspects of their work and fostering a more efficient research process overall. As a result, this innovative tool not only enhances productivity but also aids in the advancement of knowledge within various academic fields.

With the advent of ChatGPT and other neural networks, it has become apparent that the professional activities of a scientist or researcher will no longer be what they used to be in the foreseeable future. Artificial intelligence will make its own adjustments, somewhere simplifying the researcher's work, and somewhere requiring new skills and competencies. Obviously, despite some failures discussed in this article, neural networks can in many ways facilitate the routine work of a researcher from material selection and bibliography to analytical work. At the same time, only the competence of the researcher will make it possible to productively use the full potential of artificial intelligence in scientific work and to distinguish real research from pseudoscientific research. It is with this premise in mind that it is necessary to teach modern students to use

ChatGPT in research work in a foreign language course, so that it can be a faithful and reliable assistant, and by no means a genie invisibly for others doing all the work.

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